

Studies on the Genus *Piper*. V. Chemical Investigation of *Piper methysticum* Forst (Piperaceae)*. Structure and Synthesis of Flavokawain-C

C. P. DUTTA, LALA P. K. ROY and (Mrs.) A CHATTERJEE**

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal
and

D. N. ROY

Faculty of Forestry, University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada

Manuscript received 10 May 1975 ; accepted 2 November 1976

The structure of flavokawain-C(I), a minor chalcone constituent of *Piper methysticum* Forst, has been elucidated from spectroscopic studies and chemical reactions and subsequently confirmed by its synthesis and correlation with compounds of known structures. Pyridine is used for the first time for the isomerization of the chalcone to the corresponding flavanone.

THE thick, knotty roots of *Piper methysticum* Forst, popularly known as 'Kawa' or 'Kava' have been held in high esteem by the Polynesians from ancient times for its use in the preparation of slightly narcotic and intoxicating drink. It also acts as sedative, soporific and hypnotic¹.

Earlier investigations²⁻⁷ led to the isolation of several alkaloid amides, chalcones, lactones and various types of aromatic acids. Exhaustive studies on the roots of *P. methysticum* culminated in the isolation and structure elucidation of a new chalcone, flavokawain-C(I) in addition to yangonin (III), kawain (IV), methysticin (V).

Part of the work dealing with the characterization of flavokawain-C (I) has been published^{8,9}. The present communication is concerned with the details of our previous work and the synthesis of flavokawain-C.

Flavokawain-C, $C_{17}H_{16}O_6$ (M^+ , 300), m.p. 195°-196°, isolated from benzene extract as bright orange needles gave a violet colouration with $FeCl_3$ solution. The negative Shinoda test and the UV absorption maxima at 245, 265 and 370 nm ($\log \epsilon$, 3.86, 4.39 and 4.59) indicated it to be a chalcone having similar chromophoric group as that of flavokawain A¹⁰. IR spectra of the compound revealed the presence of a chelated OH (3380 cm^{-1}), conjugated carbonyl (1640 cm^{-1}), *trans* configuration of $-CH=CH$ (1610 and 986 cm^{-1}) and 1,4-disubstituted benzene nucleus (825 cm^{-1}).

The 60 MHz. PMR spectrum of flavokawain-C, exhibited the characteristic chemical shifts for an A_2B_2 system due to four aromatic protons around $\delta 6.90$ (2H, d, $J=10\text{ Hz.}$) and $\delta 7.54$ (2H, d, $J=10\text{ Hz.}$). The two phenolic hydroxyl protons appeared as sharp singlets at $\delta 8.45$ and 14.35 (both disappeared on D_2O exchange) respectively suggesting

* Golden Jubilee Session of 'Indian Chemical Society and Convention of Chemists', (1973), Abstract, p. 158.
** Present Address—Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, Calcutta, West Bengal, India.

thereby that only one OH (δ 14.35) is *ortho* to the carbonyl¹¹. Two narrowly split doublets ($J=2$ Hz.) around δ 5.71 and 6.06 (1H each) revealed the presence of two *meta* hydrogens in an aromatic nucleus. The sharp singlets at δ 3.88 and 3.95 (3H each) obviously represented the two methoxyls at slightly different environment. Two *trans* olefinic protons of the compound appeared as doublet around δ 7.63 (2H, $J=16$ Hz.) instead of the usual double doublets of the chalcone system.

On treatment with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine flavokawain-C furnished a diacetate $C_{21}H_{20}O_7$ (M^+ , 384), m.p. 142°-145°. The diacetate lacked the broad band at 3380 cm^{-1} present in the parent compound, but showed new absorptions at 1701 and 1718 cm^{-1} attributed to the two acetate groups. The PMR spectrum of the flavokawain-C diacetate, however, exhibited the characteristic double doublets around 6.90 and 7.50 δ (1H each, $J=16$ Hz.) for α - and β -protons of the chalcone system in addition to its usual signals for acetates at 2.20 and 2.30 δ in lieu of the two phenolic hydroxyl proton signals in the original compound.

Catalytic hydrogenation of the compound gave a dihydroderivative, $C_{17}H_{18}O_5$ (M^+ 302) which lacks the characteristic PMR signals for two *trans* olefinic protons of the chalcone. The symmetrical absorption of 4H centered around 2.95 and 3.17 δ ($J=6$ Hz.) is consistent with AA', BB' pattern of the sequence $-CO CH_2-CH_2-Ph$ ¹².

Characteristic mass fragmentation peaks at 207 (M^+-93) and 181 (M^+-119) coupled with doublets around 6.90 and 7.54 δ , typical of A_2B_2 system suggested the presence of monosubstituted nature of the ring B of the chalcone. Flavokawain-C was readily isomerized to the corresponding flavanone, $C_{17}H_{16}O_5$, m.p. 175-177° with pyridine¹³ or sodium acetate in methanol¹⁰. IR spectrum of the flavanone (II) exhibited characteristic bands for phenolic OH (3390 cm^{-1}), carbonyl (1634 cm^{-1}) and 1,4-disubstituted benzene nucleus (814 cm^{-1}). The UV spectrum [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 225 and 280 nm. ($\log \epsilon$, 4.34 and 4.13)] resembles closely to that of naringin¹⁴. Moreover, the band at 225 nm does not undergo any bathochromic shift with fused sodium acetate precluding the presence of free phenolic hydroxyl group at C-7. PMR spectrum of the compound showed chemical shifts characteristic of flavanone having a pair of doublets around 6.97 and 7.33 δ (2H each, $J=10$ Hz.) for an A_2B_2 system of a 1',4'-substituted ring B. The protons of the γ -pyrone ring constituted an ABX pattern in which AB part (C-3H_{Aeq} and C-3H_{Bax}) appeared around 2.82 and 3.03 δ as multiplets and X-part (C-2H) appeared at double doublets around 5.40 δ ($J=4$ Hz.).

The 70 ev mass spectrum of the flavanone like its progenitor also exhibited besides molecular ion peak at m/e 300, two prominent and diagnostic peaks

at m/e 207 ($M^+-C_6H_4(OH)$) and 181 ($M^+-HO-C_6H_4-CH=CH-$) thereby adducing further proof that the ring B of the flavanone is substituted by a hydroxyl group and that no substitution is present in the γ -pyrone ring.

Based on these spectral and chemical evidences, the structure of the flavanone may be expressed as (II) which was further confirmed by converting the flavanone to naringenin trimethyl ether¹⁵ m.p. 114° with dimethylsulphate and dry acetone in presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 .

Flavokawain-C on boiling with 10% aqueous NaOH furnished 4,6-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy acetophenone, thereby providing additional and direct chemical evidence in favour of the above conclusion and established the structure of flavokawain-C as 4',6'-dimethoxy-2',4-dihydroxy chalcone (I). The structure (I) received further confirmation from its transformation to monomethyl derivative, $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$ m.p. 112°, which was found to be identical with synthetic flavokawain-A.¹⁰

Confirmation for the structure (I) assigned to flavokawain-C also received unequivocal support from its mass spectrum which rendered diagnostic peaks at m/e 300 (M^+), 299, 272, 207, 181 (base peak) 180, 166, 152, 147, 145, 119, 138 and 95.

An independent evidence in favour of the structure of the chalcone was secured from its unambiguous synthesis. 4,6-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy acetophenone was condensed with *p*-hydroxy benzaldehyde in presence of alkali to yield flavokawain-C.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. UV spectra were measured in Carl Zeiss VSU-2 instrument in 95% EtOH. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord using KBr pellets. Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was normally used for drying organic solvents, silica gel G was used for TLC and iodine was used for developing.

Isolation

Air dried pulverized roots (1 kg.) were extracted with petrol (b.p. 60°-80°) for 20 hr. The extract upon concentration and cooling furnished yellow solid (12.0 g) which was found to be a mixture of two components. The solid was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over silica gel. The earlier fractions of benzene: chloroform (9:1) eluates furnished yangonin, m.p. 152°-154° (6.5 g.), while the later fractions of the same solvent mixtures (3:1) afforded methysticin, m.p. 134°-136° (4.0 g.).

The mother liquor left after the separation of solid was purified by chromatography over silica gel,

when kawain, m.p. 110° (2 g.) migrated out with petrol. Benzene : Chloroform mixture eluates yielded a further crop of yangonin and methysticin respectively.

The defatted roots were then exhaustively extracted with benzene. The extract was concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel. Benzene: Chloroform (1 : 1) fraction yielded an oily residue which upon purification by preparative TLC over silica gel G with Chloroform:Methanol (5 : 1) developer furnished methysticin (0.75 g.) and a new chalcone flavokawain-C, m.p. 195-196° (0.07 g.) (Found: C, 67.81, H, 5.44. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8$ requires: C, 68.00, H, 5.33%).

Acetylation of flavokawain-C

Flavokawain-C (30 mg.) was dissolved in pyridine (5 ml.) and treated with AC_2O (3 ml.). The reaction mixture was heated on water bath for 2 hr. and left at room temperature for 20 hr. The mixture was poured into ice with vigorous shaking when solid separated out. This was taken up in ether (150 ml.). The organic layer was made free from pyridine. Solid obtained on removal of ether crystallised from chloroform methanol mixture in white needles (20 mg.), m.p. 140°. (Found: C, 65.62; H, 5.28. $C_{21}H_{20}O_7$ requires: C, 65.62, H, 5.20%). *PMR*: δ : 2.20 (s, O.CO. CH_3), 2.30 (s, O.CO. CH_3), 3.87 (s, OCH_3), 3.90 (s, OCH_3), 6.34 and 6.46 (d, $J=2$ Hz.) two *meta* aromatic proton), 6.90 and 7.50 (d, $J=16$ Hz., $-CH=CH-$), 7.20 and 7.60 (q, $J=10$ Hz.) four *ortho* aromatic protons).

Dihydroflavokawain-C

Flavokawain-C (30 mg.) dissolved in ethanol (20 ml.) was shaken for 6 hrs. in an atmosphere of hydrogen in presence of Adams PtO_2 catalyst (10 mg.), pre-reduced with hydrogen. The catalyst was filtered off. Evaporation of the solvent yielded a syrupy liquid which was purified by column chromatography using silica gel as adsorbent and benzene as eluates. The purified solid was finally crystallised from benzene-petrol mixture as fine needles, (22 mg.), m.p. 109-110°. (Found: C, 67.44, H, 6.10. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8$ requires: C, 67.54, H, 6.00%).

Isomerization of flavokawain-C

a) With pyridine

Flavokawain-C (250 mg.) was refluxed with pyridine (6 ml.) at 140° for 6-8 hr and left overnight at room temperature. The product was poured into cold water, acidified with HCl (1*N*) and extracted with ether. The ether extract upon washing, drying and removal of the solvent afforded solid residue which was dissolved in EtOAc and chromatographed over silica gel (50 g.).

The fractions obtained from benzene eluent afforded unchanged flavokawain-C (170 mg.). The

pale yellow solid obtained from benzene:ethylacetate (3 : 1) eluates upon repeated crystallisations from petrol: EtOAc mixture gave white granules, m.p. 175-177°. (Found: C, 67.80, H, 5.42. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8$ requires: C, 68.00, H, 5.33%). *PMR*: ($CDCl_3$): δ 2.82 (1H, d, $J=4$ Hz. C-3 H_{ax}), 3.03 (1H, d, $J=4$ Hz. C-3 H_{ax}), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.92 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$), 5.40 (1H, dd, C-2H), 6.13 (2H, s, Aromatic), 6.97 and 7.33 (each 2H, d, $J=10$ Hz., Aromatic), 8.09 (1H, s, disappeared on D_2O exchange, Phenolic OH). Mass *m/e* 300 (M^+), 299, 272, 207, 206, 181, 180, 166, 152 (base peak), 147, 137, 120, 119, 109, 107 and 94.

b) With NaOAc

A mixture of flavokawain-C (100 mg.), dissolved in methanol (10 ml.) and fused NaOAc (1.0 g.) was refluxed for 4 hrs. The solution was filtered and the filtrate on evaporation yielded semisolid residue which upon chromatographic purification over silica gel and repeated crystallizations with petrol:EtOAc gave the flavanone, m.p. 175-177°.

Alkali hydrolysis of flavokawain-C

A solution of flavokawain-C (100 mg.) in 10% aqueous NaOH solution (10 ml.) was refluxed at 140° for 2 hr. and allowed to stand at room temperature for 15 hrs. The product was poured in water, cooled and acidified with HCl (1*N*) and extracted with ether. The organic layer on washing, drying and evaporation furnished white solid (20 mg.) which upon crystallisation from methanol gave 2-hydroxy-4, 6-dimethoxy acetophenone, m.p. 80°.

Synthesis of flavokawain-C

The mixture of 2-hydroxy-4, 6-dimethoxy acetophenone (4.8 g.) and *p*-hydroxy benzaldehyde (5.0 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (50 ml.) and flashed with N_2 for 15 min. NaOH (12.0 g.) dissolved in minimum quantity of water was then added and the resulting mixture was refluxed on a water bath in N_2 atmosphere for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was kept overnight in an atmosphere of N_2 at room temperature. The product was poured in cold water (200 ml.), acidified with dil. HCl and extracted with ether (250 ml.). The ether extract upon washing, drying and evaporation yielded an oily residue which was subsequently crystallized from methanol in orange needles, m.p. 195-196° (4.00 g.).

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. P. Sengupta, Head of the Department of Chemistry for his encouragement. Financial assistances from University of Kalyani and University of Calcutta are gratefully acknowledged.

DUTTA, ROY, CHATTERJEE AND ROY, STUDIES ON THE GENUS *PIPER*. V. CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION ETC.

References

1. R. C. WREN, M. HOLMES, H. POTTER and W. WREN, Protter's Encyclopaedia of Botanical Drugs and Preparations. Potter and Clarke, London, 1941, p. 195.
2. W. BORSCHKE and C. K. BONDESTAIN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 2515.
3. M. W. KLOHS, F. KELLER, R. E. WILLIAMS, M.I. TOEKES and G. E. Cronheim, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1959, **1**, 95 and references cited therein.
4. H. ACHENBACH and W. KARL, *Chem. Ber.*, 1970, **103**, 2535.
5. H. ACHENBACH and G. WITTMANN, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1970, 3259.
6. L. CSUPOR, *Arch. Pharmz.*, 1970, **303**, 975.
7. H. ACHENBACH and W. KARL, *Chem. Ber.*, 1971, **104**, 1468.
8. C.P. DUTTA, Lala P. K. Roy, A. CHATTERJEE and D. N. Roy, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, **11**, 2891.
9. C. P. Dutta, lala P. K. Roy, A. Chatterjee and D. N. Roy, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 509.
10. R. Haensel, G. Ranft and P. Baehr, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1963, **18b**, 370.
11. D. J. Rengshaw and H. J. Smith, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1965, 1383.
12. G. Cardillo, L. Marlini and R. Mondelli, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, **24**, 495.
13. C. P. Dutta and Lala P. K. Roy, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1975 (in press.)
14. T. Kariyone and T. Matsuno *J. Pharm. Soc. (Japan)*, 1955, **74** 363.
15. F. Kaufmann and J. Lam, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1967, **21**, 311.